

CIRCE 3rd Project Quality Report

01/01/2024 - 30/06/2024

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Executive Summary

The CIRCE Project Quality Report summarizes the results of the project internal activity of monitoring the quality of project management. This third report refers to months 13 - 18 of the project, from 01/01/2024 to 30/06/2024.

The results of this third round of consultations show on the one hand a decline in participation (9 responses versus 14 in the second quality report) and on the other hand relatively less satisfaction with the way management and implementation activities were conducted.

Disclaimer

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1. Introduction

A questionnaire was distributed among all project partners to assess their degree of satisfaction towards the management staff and activities. The questionnaire replicated the expanded structure of the one used for the second quality assessment period, including questions related to aspects that will be reported about in the Final report. For confidentiality purposes, it was possible to complete the questionnaire anonymously.

The questionnaire contained 15 questions. Specifically, five questions asked the partners to rate the project management on a 1 to 5 scale from the point of view of overall satisfaction, effectiveness and efficacy of communication, degree of cooperation, conflict resolution abilities, and resource management. Two yes/no questions were aimed at evaluating the management's communication capacity and leadership. Four questions offered the opportunity to provide more details about the various aspects under assessment.

Implementation and dissemination were also assessed with two questions each.

A final question provided the opportunity to freely express additional comments, suggestions, or feedback regarding the project overall activities.

The results of the questionnaire are presented below. The results of this third round of consultations show on the one hand a decline in participation (9 responses versus 14 in the second quality report) and on the other hand relatively less satisfaction with the way management and implementation activities were conducted. The first figure can be interpreted in many different ways: disaffection with the project, fatigue related to the time of year and workload, or lack of confidence in the effectiveness of the tool. Regarding the decrease in overall satisfaction with project management and implementation activities, we believe that the publication of this report is an important time for discussion and comparison. As is customary, in the last section of this report we indicate some possible strategies for resolution.

2. Results

2.1 General satisfaction on Management

1. On a scale of 1 to 5, please rate your overall satisfaction with the project management activities:
9 risposte

Comparison with previous report:

1. On a scale of 1 to 5, please rate your overall satisfaction with the project management activities:
14 risposte

2.2 Communication and Cooperation

4. How do you evaluate project communication and cooperation?

9 risposte

3. Is the project management team adequately defining and communicating project goals, objectives, and deadlines?

9 risposte

2. How would you rate the effectiveness of communication channels established by the project management team (e.g., emails, newsletter, meetings, project shared space)?

9 risposte

Comparison with previous report:

4. How do you evaluate project communication and cooperation?

14 risposte

3. Is the project management team adequately defining and communicating project goals, objectives, and deadlines?

14 risposte

2. How would you rate the effectiveness of communication channels established by the project management team (e.g., emails, newsletter, meetings, project shared space)?

14 risposte

2.2.1 Detailed comments on communication and cooperation channels.

Some dissatisfaction was expressed regarding the use of Google Meet and Google Drive as platforms for meetings and document sharing.

The use of alternative means to email for direct communication was also proposed.

Other comments, however, express satisfaction and appreciation for the communication channels that have been created, particularly the newsletter and detailed minutes.

2.2.2 Positive and negative elements of the communication and cooperation processes.

Positive: The team and management have a positive and cooperative relationship overall. The newsletter is an excellent way to stay informed about tasks, meetings, and deadlines. Efforts are consistently made to keep everyone connected and informed. Despite natural and expected differences in opinion, the processes are running smoothly. Team members are kept well-informed about updates and changes, aiding in smooth transitions.

Negative: Navigating Google Drive can be challenging, and the guidelines aren't always clear, especially for those unfamiliar with ERASMUS, such as the requirements for reports or changes to WP 4 outcomes mid-project. Concern is voiced that some emails, from both project management and partners, have a passive-aggressive tone. There should be clearer and more direct communication about any frustrations that arise among partners. Excessive bureaucracy sometimes hampers cooperation and workflow. With the numerous meetings and tasks, it's difficult for everyone to attend every meeting. Despite the team's cooperative nature, there are delays in collaborative responses, which hinder the project's progress. Some partners don't reply to emails, and some WP leaders rarely communicate. This isn't due to the project management team but rather individual partners and WP leaders.

2.3 Conflict resolution

7. How would you rate the project management team's ability to handle and resolve issues and conflicts within the project?

9 risposte

Comparison with previous report:

7. How would you rate the project management team's ability to handle and resolve issues and conflicts within the project?

14 risposte

2.4 Leadership

9. Is the project management team demonstrating effective leadership so far?

9 risposte

Comparison with previous report:

9. Is the project management team demonstrating effective leadership so far?

14 risposte

2.5 Resource management

10. How well is the project management team managing resources (e.g., budget, personnel, equipment)?

9 risposte

Comparison with previous report:

10. How well is the project management team managing resources (e.g., budget, personnel, equipment)?

14 risposte

2.6 Difficulties encountered

The report submission process was challenging due to unclear guidelines. The project lacked pre-agreed goals, guidelines, and methodologies for individual work packages, leading to ongoing discussions and negotiations, which complicates coordination across different countries and schedules. While better planning was needed from the start, the focus now must be on flexibility and practicality to manage the situation. The main challenge is handling numerous overlapping tasks due to delays. Keeping up with frequent meetings and decisions is difficult, especially if someone misses a meeting. Although minutes and newsletters help, they are not always reviewed promptly. Overall, there are too many concurrent tasks with overlapping timelines.

2.7 Implementation

11. What is your overall satisfaction with the results of the implemented work packages?

9 risposte

Comparison with previous report:

11. What is your overall satisfaction with the results of the implemented work packages?

14 risposte

2.7.1 Main global and WP-related issues

- Mismatch between project deadlines and school year requirements.
- Excessive decision processes for some WPs and/or lack of adequate planning.
- Excessive delays on some tasks, with a cascade effect on following tasks. There is a concrete risk of missing the deadlines.
- There is a clear discrepancy between planning and outcome, which causes some frustration.
- Too much time devoted to technical and legal issues, which takes time and energy from more substantial work.
- None of the activities have been fully completed halfway through the project.

- On WP2:
 - WP2 initially faced interpersonal and content-related issues, but these challenges appear to have been resolved successfully.
 - WP2 is significantly behind schedule, causing delays and issues with WP3.
 - Previous ineffective leadership in WP2 has improved, with Karoline's recent meeting being notably more productive.
 - WP2 implementation has become more consistent, but intermittent communication from the leaders creates a sense of project neglect.
- On WP4:
 - WP4 seems to be planned in retrospect which complicates things but the products are amazing.

2.8 Dissemination

13. How satisfied are you with the results of the dissemination activities?

9 risposte

Comparison with previous report:

13. How satisfied are you with the results of the dissemination activities?

14 risposte

2.8.1 Detailed comments on dissemination activities.

The social media team is performing exceptionally well, and the Italian team, along with those responsible for social media, are doing an excellent job. I expect that once we obtain the results from WPs 2, 3, and 4, our dissemination activities will significantly increase. However, there appears to be a noticeable imbalance in the dissemination efforts among the partners.

2.9 Final remarks and suggestions

While it's understandable that deadlines create pressure, it should be remembered that all are doing their best within their unique circumstances. It's important to acknowledge that some current difficulties and delays could have been avoided with better planning in the project's early stages, including by the management and all partners. The deadlines for tasks and work packages will need to be renegotiated. It is crucial to simplify the tasks ahead; otherwise a struggle with a heavy workload in a short timeframe will continue. The new German colleague, who appears practical and straightforward, was a pleasant surprise; she might help bring order to a somewhat hesitant partner.

3. Summary: Critical points and room for improvement

Request: Change the platform used for meetings

Recovery measure: The platform used for the meetings is the one provided by Siena University (which uses both Gmeet and Webex). If partners have access to other platforms and want to make them available to the project, they are welcome to do so, organizing all the plenary meetings on behalf of the coordinator.

Request: Provide a how-to or checklist for final reporting

Recovery measure: The management team will make sure that for the Final Report, a detailed guide and checklist is circulated well before the deadline with clear indication of the required information.

Request: Consider a re-planning of activities and re-negotiation of WP tasks and deadlines

Recovery measure: A re-planning of activities is definitely needed. At the September plenary meeting, the re-planning proposals made by WP leaders will be discussed and approved.

Request: Simplify current and upcoming tasks

Recovery measure: See above.

Request: Reduce time spent on technical and legal issues

Recovery measure: Regarding legal aspects, it is worth mentioning that the project includes a partner (IBU), for which European agreements do not apply. We believe that the in-depth study of the legal issue and the solutions adopted represent an added value of the project, as well as capital for future collaborations with non-EU countries. We will open a discussion on what is meant by “technical aspects”.

Request: Adopt a nicer and more respectful tone in emails

Recovery measure: Adopting a respectful tone is the duty of all partners, and everyone is asked to pay attention so that no one can feel offended. It is possible that some degree of misunderstanding is due to cultural and linguistic misalignment. It is good practice to respond promptly to emails to avoid feelings of frustration that can then lead to the use of inappropriate tones.